

Eventually, the affected leaf blade withered and dropped off.

The causal organism was isolated on potato dextrose agar. A pathogenicity test was performed by placing a drop of mycelial fragment prepared from 7-d-old culture at the collar region during

the late booting stage. Affected collar regions were collected and placed in sterile petri dishes lined with moist filter paper.

The fungus produced numerous pycnidia on the affected tissue. Pycnidia were dark, separated, immersed in host

tissue, and ostiolate. Conidia were hyaline, oblong, rounded at both ends, 14-15 × 4 µm.

The causal fungus was identified as *Ascochyta oryzae* Catt. This is the first record of its occurrence in Manipur. ■

Effect of some leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia

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In the crop rotation pattern of Pakistan, rice usually follows wheat. Leguminous crops which have the ability to restore soil fertility by fixing N from atmosphere also are planted as dry season crops.

We studied the effect on rice of growing a leguminous crop in soil infested with sclerotia of *S. oryzae* (the cause of stem rot in rice). Wheat was planted as a control. The experiment was laid out in a complete block design with four replications.

Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) gram (*Cicer arietinum*), lentil (*Lens*

Table 1. Effect of leguminous crops on number and viability of *Sclerotium oryzae* sclerotia. ^a Sheikhupura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation ^b	1986 wet season		1986-87 dry season		1987 wet season	
	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)	Population	Viability (%)
R-W-R	9 a	63 a	8 a	70 a	8 a	87 a
R-L-R	8 a	60 a	10 a	78 a	7 a	74 a
R-G-R	9 a	52 a	10 a	64 a	13 a	83 a
R-B-R	14 b	73 a	8 a	41 b	6 a	89 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test. ^b R = rice, W = wheat, L = lentil, G = gram, B = berseem.

culinaris), and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) were planted in Nov and harvested in Apr. Rice (*Oryza sativa*) was transplanted in Jun and harvested in Oct. Recommended NPK was applied. Sclerotia were separated from soil by sieving and flotation technique after harvest of each crop. Their viability was tested on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at 3,000 ppm each.

Population and viability were reduced up to 43% after berseem; there were no significant reductions in sclerotia after

Table 2. Effect of a leguminous crop on rice yield. Sheikhupura, Pakistan.

Crop rotation	Rice yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield Increase (%)
Wheat - rice	5.1 c	-
Lentil - rice	5.2 bc	3
Gram - rice	6.0 b	17
Berseem - rice	6.9 a	35

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P < 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

rice (Table 1). Rice yields increased significantly when berseem was used in the rotation (Table 2). ■

Etiology of grain discoloration in upland rice in West Sumatra

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Rice grain discoloration is becoming a serious problem in tropical rice production areas, particularly in upland rice. In Indonesia, it is common to find the disease in upland rice grown in acid soils, such as the red-yellow Podzolic soils of West Sumatra.

We collected seeds of susceptible upland rice cultivar Tondano and panicles of local upland rice cultivars Arias and Simariti showing different levels of disease severity. The seeds were seeded after the agar plate test and incubated in a

Microorganisms associated with grain discoloration levels (1, 10, 30, 60, 100%) in upland rice. West Sumatra, Indonesia.

Microorganism	Microorganisms (%) at indicated level of grain discoloration				
	1%	10%	30%	60%	100%
<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>	14 ^a	17	22	41	40
<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	50	30	14	5	7
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	12	34	24	30	2
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	12	8	13	8	7
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	9	7	15	7	8
<i>Torula</i> sp.	3	1	1	3	9
<i>Mycovellosiella oryzae</i>	1	4	0	3	0
<i>Cercospora janseana</i>	2	2	0	1	0
<i>Phyllosticta</i> sp.	0	2	1	2	0
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	0	0	0	5	0
<i>Gerlachia oryzae</i>	1	0	2	0	0
<i>Phomopsis</i> sp.	0	2	0	1	0
<i>Cercospora oryzae</i>	0	0	1	2	0
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	2	0	0	0	1
<i>Gonatobotrys</i> sp.	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Macrophoma</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Memnoniella</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Helicoceras oryzae</i>	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Diplodia oryzae</i>	0	0	0	0	1

^a Data from 100 seeds.